

**APPENDIX A
INDIVIDUAL ANALYSIS**

TABLE 1
H1: The normality assumption testing.

The p-value is in grey colour when the data is NOT normally distributed.

Experiment	Data set	Variable	Normality Test Result
O-Rep	Pooled	c	p-value = 1.63e-1
		ic	p-value = 8.778e-05
	TP	c	p-value = 7.74e-1
		ic	p-value = 4.724e-05
	NTP	c	p-value = 6.22e-1
		ic	p-value = 2.289e-2
NS-Rep1	Pooled	c	p-value = 3.09e-1
		ic	p-value = 6.605e-08
	TP	c	p-value = 7.24e-1
		ic	p-value = 3.114322e-05
	NTP	c	p-value = 7.35e-1
		ic	p-value = 2.498402e-05
NS-Rep2	Pooled	c	p-value = 5.276e-1
		ic	p-value = 2.263e-9
	TP	c	p-value = 6.399e-1
		ic	p-value = 2.869e-09
	NTP	c	p-value = 5.117e-1
		ic	p-value = 7.343e-4

TABLE 2
H2: The assumptions testing.

Assumption A: Multivariate normality tested with the multivariate Shapiro-wilk test;
Assumption B: Common variance-covariance tested with the Bartlett test.

Result	Comments
O-Rep	
A p-value: NTP = 9.041e-1, TP = 3.013e-1	The natural log transformation was applied to the ic data of the TP and NTP groups to meet the multivariate normality.
B c: p-value = 3.013e-1 (df= 1), ic: p-value = 8.008e-1 (df=1)	
NS-Rep1	
A p-value: NTP = 3.247e-1, TP = 8.752e-1	The cube root transformation was applied to the ic data of the TP and NTP groups to meet the multivariate normality.
B c: p-value = 1.193e-1 (df= 1), ic: p-value = 9.97e-1 (df=1)	
NS-Rep2	
A p-value: NTP = 1.74e-1, TP = 4.821e-2	The cube root transformation was applied to the ic data of the TP and NTP groups to meet the multivariate normality.
B c: p-value = 7.214e-1 (df= 1), ic: p-value = 3.257e-1 (df=1)	

The grey value is lesser than 0.05, but it is on the edge.
Therefore, we provide a Q-Q plot to support the multivariate normality of the TP data of NS-Rep2.

TABLE 3
H3: The normality assumption testing.

Experiment	Group	Variable	Normality Test Result
O-Rep	TP	z	p-value = 6.451e-1
	NTP	z	p-value = 8.953e-1
NS-Rep1	TP	z	p-value = 9.882e-1
	NTP	z	p-value = 8.347e-1
NS-Rep2	TP	z	p-value = 3.814e-1
	NTP	z	p-value = 6.067e-1

TABLE 4
H4: The normality assumption testing.

The p-value is in grey colour when the data is NOT normally distributed.

Experiment	Group	Variable	Normality Test Result
O-Rep	TP	TD	p-value = 1.877e-3
	NTP	TD	p-value = 7.701e-2
NS-Rep1	TP	TD	p-value = 4.292e-3
	NTP	TD	p-value = 1.137e-1
NS-Rep2	TP	TD	p-value = 2.89e-2
	NTP	TD	p-value = 2.034e-1

APPENDIX B META ANALYSIS

B.1 Step 2

TABLE 5
Descriptive statistics for c : NTP vs TP.

Experiment	Group	N	Mean	SD	Median
O-Orig	NTP	21	8.142	2.669	8
	TP	21	7.142	2.031	7
O-Rep	NTP	21	7.619	3.353	7
	TP	24	6.458	2.484	7
NS-Rep1	NTP	27	8.185	3.199	8
	TP	26	6.576	2.335	7
NS-Rep2	NTP	35	10.200	3.305	11
	TP	31	9.322	3.228	9

TABLE 6
Descriptive statistics for ic : NTP vs TP.

Experiment	Group	N	Mean	SD	Median
O-Orig	NTP	21	1.238	1.670	1
	TP	21	1.142	2.056	0
O-Rep	NTP	21	2.380	1.829	3
	TP	24	1.291	1.731	1
NS-Rep1	NTP	27	1.444	1.987	1
	TP	26	1.307	1.783	0
NS-Rep2	NTP	35	3.057	2.848	2
	TP	31	0.516	1.207	0

Fig. 1. Box plots for *c* and *ic*.

Fig. 2. Profile Plots for *c* and *ic*: NTP vs TP.

B.2 Step 4

TABLE 7
Results of multilevel models.

Models: Step 4		AIC	Normality	Comments
3	F= Treatment ADE ADE*Treatment; R= INTERCEPT Site	-105.735	Yes	
4	F=Treatment ATE ATE*Treatment; R= INTERCEPT Site	-111.435	Yes	
5	F=Treatment IDE IDE*Treatment; R= INTERCEPT Site	-102.099	Yes	
6	F=Treatment ITE ITE*Treatment; R= INTERCEPT Site	-103.939	Yes	
7	F=Treatment Trainer; R= INTERCEPT Site	-120.428	Yes	Convergence Issues
8	F=Treatment Degree; R= INTERCEPT Site	-120.428	Yes	Convergence Issues
9	F=Treatment InstLang; R= INTERCEPT Site	-120.428	Yes	Hessian matrix is not positive definite
10	F=Treatment Monitor; R= INTERCEPT Site	-120.428	Yes	Hessian matrix is not positive definite
	Adding multiple contextual (more than one) variables as fixed effects to the random intercept model made it more complex.	-	-	The fixed effect calculations issued errors.
11 ¹	F=Treatment; R= INTERCEPT Treatment Site	-116.556	Yes	
12	F=Treatment Trainer; R= INTERCEPT Treatment Site	-120.428	Yes	Convergence Issues
13	F=Treatment Degree; R= INTERCEPT Treatment Site	-120.428	Yes	Hessian matrix is not positive definite
14	F=Treatment InstLang; R= INTERCEPT Treatment Site	-120.428	Yes	Hessian matrix is not positive definite
15	F=Treatment Monitor; R= INTERCEPT Treatment Site	-120.428	Yes	Hessian matrix is not positive definite
	Adding multiple contextual (more than one) variables as fixed effects to the random intercept and random slope model made it more complex.	-	-	The fixed effect calculations issued errors.
16	F=Treatment Treatment*Trainer; R= INTERCEPT Treatment Site	-116.194	Yes	Hessian matrix is not positive definite
	Adding more cross-level interactions to the previous model (Model 16) or Model 2 yielded the same observations as Model 16.	-	-	

Fig. 3. Forest Plot: English vs Serbian.

¹We built the models with five covariance matrices (CV): scaled identity, diagonal, compound symmetry, unstructured and AR(1). The fit of the models with the scaled identity was the best. Thus the table reports the AIC of the scaled identity CV model.